

Frailty and depression: Reciprocal influences or common causes?

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ABSTRACT

Background: Previous research demonstrated substantial associations between frailty and depression in late life, but it remains unclear whether this relationship is best explained by reciprocal influences of these variables or by common causes. This study investigated the interdependencies between frailty and depression across time by examining cross-lagged effects within individuals, while accounting for variability in baseline levels and long-term development between individuals.

Methods: We modeled longitudinal data from six panel waves gathered in the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, covering a time period of up to 14 years. The total sample size was $N = 58,152$ individuals aged 50 years or older. Frailty was based on a deficit accumulation frailty index and depressive symptoms were measured with the EURO-D scale. We used a latent curve model with structured residuals for statistical analysis.

Results: The results did not demonstrate relevant cross-lagged effects of frailty and depression at the within-person level. However, within-person increases in frailty were accompanied by within-person increases in depression at the same point in time. At the between-person level, it showed that individuals with higher levels and steeper trajectories in frailty also tend to show higher levels and steeper trajectories in depression.

Conclusion: These findings question the notion that frailty and depression reciprocally influence each other over the course of time, but rather indicate that frailty and depression might be both affected by common causes, in both the short and the long term.

1. Introduction

Physical and mental health interact in complex ways, and it is a challenging task to identify the underlying mechanisms of how they might influence each other. Although research demonstrates substantial associations between measures of physical and mental health (Barry et al., 2013; Chu et al., 2019; Lohman et al., 2016; Mhaoláin et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015), the causal direction of effects remains poorly understood. This study seeks to shed new light on this complex relationship by examining to which extent physical and mental health might influence each other over time and to reveal how much of the association between mental and physical health might be due to common causes or a shared vulnerability. Since health problems (both physically and mentally) are associated with ageing (e.g., Hoogendijk et al., 2017; Sutin et al., 2013), this issue is of particular importance in late life, which is why this study focuses on health in older adults.

As an indicator of the general state of health in older age, the concept of frailty has gained considerable attention in recent decades (Fried et al., 2001; Mitnitski et al., 2001). Frailty is often defined as an extreme

expression of the aging process, characterized by cumulative decline in multiple physiological systems and an elevated vulnerability to different kinds of stressors (Clegg et al., 2013; Fried et al., 2001; Hoogendijk et al., 2019). This vulnerability is also related to an increased risk of adverse outcomes, such as lower quality of life (Kojima et al., 2016), hospitalization (Kojima, 2016), or mortality (Shamliyan et al., 2013).

Frailty has been also associated with emotional distress and mental illness (Andrew and Rockwood, 2007; Mhaoláin et al., 2012). Particularly the relationship to depression has been intensively studied and debated. However, there is disagreement in the literature whether (1) frailty is a risk factor for depression (Mezuk et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015), (2) depression is a risk factor for frailty (Mezuk et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015), or (3) depression and frailty are overlapping constructs that share one or several common causes (Kamaruzzaman et al., 2010; Lohman et al., 2016, 2014). In the following, we shortly summarize previous research findings on these alternative explanations.

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1.1. Frailty as a risk factor for depression

Many longitudinal studies have demonstrated that depression might be a negative consequence of frailty (for reviews, see Mezuk et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015). This finding could indicate that frailty and the awareness of ongoing physical decline represents a major cause of emotional distress (such as feelings of worthlessness or hopelessness, Bruce, 2001), which, in turn, might result in depressive symptomatology or even depressive disorders that require treatment (Andrew and Rockwood, 2007; Jia et al., 2020; Mhaoláin et al., 2012). Less physical activity and fewer social contacts as a result of increasing frailty levels may be important intervening factors in this relationship (Penninx et al., 1999), although the causal direction of these mediating effects remains unresolved.

1.2. Depression as a risk factor for frailty

Research also highlights the role that psychosocial factors, and depression, in particular, may play in the development of poor physical health in older adults. Several empirical studies showed that baseline depression is related to an increased risk of adverse physical health outcomes at follow-up, including frailty (for reviews, see Mezuk et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015), and related indicators of physical health such as disability, reduced mobility, or functional limitations (Geerlings et al., 2001; Penninx et al., 1999; Stuck et al., 1999). The underlying mechanisms by which depression might affect physical health are unclear. Potential intervening factors include reduced physical activity (Penninx et al., 1999), antidepressant use (Lakey et al., 2012), or alterations in neuronal, hormonal, and immunological functioning (Bruce, 2001).

1.3. Depression and frailty share common causes

The above-mentioned literature supports the notion of a uni- or bi-directional dependency between frailty and depression. However, interpretations on whether frailty and depression are indeed causally related to each other are limited due to methodological weaknesses in study design (i.e., either cross-sectional studies or longitudinal studies with only two measurement points) and statistical analysis (i.e., focusing on differences between individuals rather than on changes within individuals).

An alternative explanation for the substantial association between these physical and mental health states would be that indicators of frailty and depression each belong to overlapping domains of the same construct. Indeed, depressive symptoms are often used as one of several dimensions that make up the frailty measure (Romero-Ortuno and Kenny, 2012; Searle et al., 2008). Lohman et al. (2016) performed confirmatory factor analysis on indicators of both depression and frailty and found that these constructs are best modeled as two distinct, but highly correlated factors. Utilising latent class analysis, it was further demonstrated that frailty and depression represent two separate constructs, although there was relatively high overlap between populations that are categorized as both frail and depressed (Lohman et al., 2014; Mezuk et al., 2013). These findings suggest that frailty and depression capture distinct aspects of health, even though these aspects are highly related to each other. The interdependence between these two constructs may be explained by influences of common causes that exert similar effects on both frailty and depression. In other words, frailty and depression may share a common vulnerability to the same stressors, which finally results in a positive relationship between these two constructs (Lohman et al., 2016).

1.4. Scope of the current study

In this study, we examined the interdependence between frailty and depression over the course of time. To this end, we analyzed repeated

measures of both frailty and depression from a multi-wave cohort study covering a time period of several years in late life. Our analysis was based on a multilevel structural equation modeling approach that included both a cross-lagged structure and a growth curve component (Bollen and Curran, 2004; Curran et al., 2014). The cross-lagged structure captures mechanisms that occur within individuals, thus representing within-person effects. In other words, it is examined whether intra-individual variations in frailty are associated with both concurrent and time-adjacent intra-individual variations in depression. The growth curve component examines the extent to which the individual levels and long-term developments of frailty and depression are related to each other. These effects capture inter-individual variability in intra-individual stability and growth over time, and thus represent between-person effects (Curran et al., 2014). The key asset of this approach is that it explicitly differentiates mechanisms that happen within individuals from processes that manifest between individuals. This allows us to draw more substantive conclusions about the direction of effects and potentially confounding factors.

Based on the literature reviewed above, we define specific hypotheses for the relationship between frailty and depression. These hypotheses are not mutually exclusive and might represent separate processes that complement each other. As regards the bi-directional association between frailty and depression, we outline two hypotheses that reflect processes at the within-person level:

H1a. Within-person increases in frailty at a specific point in time go along with within-person increases in depression at a subsequent point in time.

H1b. Within-person increases in depression at a specific point in time go along with within-person increases in frailty at a subsequent point in time.

The hypothesized effect that frailty and depression are both determined by common causes may demonstrate in different ways, depending on whether the correlation shows at the within-person (*H2*) or the between-person (*H3/H4*) level:

H2. Within-person increases in frailty at a specific point in time are associated with within-person increases in depression at the same point in time.

H3. Individuals who show higher levels in frailty tend to show higher levels in depression.

H4. Individuals who show steeper trajectories in frailty tend to show steeper trajectories in depression.

2. Methods

2.1. Design and data

We used longitudinal data gathered in the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE; Börsch-Supan et al., 2013), which provides panel data representative of community-dwelling individuals aged 50 years or older from multiple European countries and Israel. Most of the data are collected using face-to-face computer-aided personal interviewing (CAPI) and comprise health-related and socioeconomic variables. To date, SHARE includes six regular panel waves (excluding Wave 3, which focuses on life histories): Wave 1 (years 2004/05), Wave 2 (2006/07), Wave 4 (2011/12), Wave 5 (2013), Wave 6 (2015), and Wave 7 (2017), covering a period of up to 14 years (Börsch-Supan, 2019a,b,c,d,e,f). Moreover, refresher samples are drawn to compensate for sample attrition in the longitudinal database. In this study, we included both baseline and refresher samples. Since the current study focuses on relationships over time, we restricted the sample to participants who provide at least two repeated observations for both depression and frailty. The total sample size finally amounted to $N = 58,152$ individuals from 17 European countries and Israel (for more

detailed country information, see Bergmann et al., 2019).

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Frailty

Frailty was operationalized using the frailty index (FI), a measure based on the accumulation of health deficits approach (Mitnitski et al., 2001; Rockwood and Mitnitski, 2007; Searle et al., 2008). Deficits are usually defined to include symptoms, diseases, disabilities, and laboratory abnormalities (Hoogendijk et al., 2019). We selected 44 items that measure health deficits and which were available in all six waves (for more details, see Table A1 in the electronic supplementary materials). Each item was coded as either “0 = deficit not present” or “1 = deficit present”. Item scores were summed up for each individual and divided by the total number of valid answers (provided that at least 40 values were available). Thus, the frailty index ranges between 0 and 1, where higher scores indicate higher frailty levels.

2.2.2. Depressive symptoms

SHARE employs the EURO-D scale, a reliable and valid scale of depressive symptoms (DS) initially developed to compare depression in late life across several European countries (Prince et al., 1999a,b). The EURO-D comprises 12 dichotomous items capturing the absence or presence of the following depressive symptoms: sadness, pessimism, suicidal feelings, guilt, sleeping problems, loss of interest, irritability, loss of appetite, fatigue, lack of concentration, lack of enjoyment, and tearfulness. Each item is scored as either “0 = symptom not present” or “1 = symptom present”. These item scores are summed up to a total scale score with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 12, where greater scores indicate more depressive symptoms.

2.2.3. Additional variables

Additional variables were sex (females vs. males), age groups (50–55, 56–60, 61–65, and >65 years), and educational level based on the international standard classification of education (ISCED; low = levels 0–2, medium = levels 3–4, and high = levels 5–6). These variables were used for multiple group analysis.

2.3. Modeling strategy

To test our hypotheses, we employed a multilevel structural equation modeling approach based on the latent curve model with structured residuals (LCM-SR; Curran et al., 2014). The LCM-SR has been proposed as an extension to the autoregressive latent trajectory model (Bollen and Curran, 2004), which allows to combine growth curve and cross-lagged panel modeling. The key advantage of the LCM-SR is that the inclusion of a time-specific residual structure allows to explicitly separate within- and between-person effects (Curran et al., 2014).

A graphical representation of the bivariate LCM-SR for the FI and DS across the period under investigation is provided in Fig. 1. The growth curve component of this model captures between-person variability in both the individual initial levels and trends, represented by the random intercept (RI) and random slope (RS) factors, respectively. The factor loadings on the RS factors are fixed to the constants 0, 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6, such that the weights reflect the time of measurement (with Wave 1 defined as baseline and skipping the weight for Wave 3) and to specify a positive linear trend for both the FI and DS over time. The cross-lagged panel component provides information on autoregressive, cross-lagged, and within-time associations of the residuals. As the residual structure captures time-specific deviations from both the person-specific levels and trends, these associations reflect within-person dynamics within and

Fig. 1. Latent curve model with structured residuals (Curran et al., 2014) for the frailty index (FI) and depressive symptoms (DS) across waves 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, and 7 (w1, w2, w4, w5, w6, and w7). Rectangles and ellipses denote manifest and latent variables, respectively. Circles are residuals, and triangles denote constants (i.e., representing the means of the random factors). Single-headed arrows represent regressions and two-headed arrows covariances. Paths labeled with numbers show regression effects fixed at the respective number. RI = random intercept. RS = random slope. L = latent variable. R = residual.

between the FI and DS.

As an additional analysis, we conducted multiple group analysis in terms of sex, age groups, and educational levels for the final best-fitting model. This allows us to examine whether the final model holds across different subpopulations and to which extent the within- and between-person effects differ as a function of sex, age, and education.

2.4. Statistical analysis

Model estimation was conducted using full information maximum likelihood (FIML), with robust Huber-White standard errors and a scaled χ^2 -test statistic. FIML estimates the model by using all information that is available from each individual and is often considered the preferred method for handling missing data in structural equation modeling (e.g., Allison, 2003). We consider a substantial part of the data missing at random (MAR; Little and Rubin, 2002), since we assume the propensity for missing data on a specific variable (e.g., frailty at Wave 7) to be determined, at least to a large extent, by other observed variables in the analysis (e.g., frailty at waves 1–6).

For model fit evaluation, the robust variants of the Tucker-Lewis-index (TLI), the comparative-fit-index (CFI), the standardized root mean square residual (SRMR), and the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) with 90% confidence intervals, as well as the Akaike and the sample-size adjusted Bayesian information criterion are reported (AIC and BIC, respectively; Akaike, 1974; Schwarz, 1978). We considered a TLI and a CFI of ≥ 0.95 , and a SRMR and a RMSEA of ≤ 0.06 to be indicative of adequate model fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). We used R 3.4.4 (R Core Team, 2018) for basic statistical analysis, and the R-packages lavaan 0.6–3 (Rosseel, 2012) and semTools 0.5–1 (Jorgensen et al., 2018) for model testing. Due to the large number of observations, model fit comparisons were performed at an alpha level of 0.001%. For parameter interpretation, we focused on the effect size rather than the statistical significance.

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

The average age of respondents (at Wave 1) was 62.2 years ($SD = 8.7$; range = 50–99), and 55% of respondents were female; 45% had a low level of education, 35% a medium level, and 20% a high level of education. On average, respondents provided 3.5 ($SD = 1.2$; range = 2–6) repeated observations for the FI, and 3.1 ($SD = 1.3$; range = 2–6) repeated observations for DS. Descriptive statistics, pairwise correlations, total numbers of observations, and reliability estimates for the FI

and DS across waves are shown in Table 1.

3.2. Model development and testing

For model development, we tested five competing models with increasing complexity. First, we specified a model without random effects. More specifically, we defined an LCM-SR as illustrated in Fig. 1, but we excluded the RS factors and imposed the constraint of zero variance to the RI factors (Model 1). This model resembles traditional cross-lagged panel modeling (i.e., autoregressive and cross-lagged effects, but no growth curve component). Second, we relaxed the constraint for the RI factors and freely estimated their variance for both the FI and DS (Model 2). As a consequence, individuals were allowed to vary over time around their person-specific levels, rather than around the group-specific levels as defined in Model 1. Third, we added the RS factors to the model, where individuals were not only allowed to fluctuate around their own person-specific levels, but also around their own person-specific trajectories. In Models 3a and 3b, we included the RS factors separately for the FI and DS, respectively. Model 3c included RS factors for both constructs.

Model fit statistics can be found in Table 2. Based on the scaled χ^2 -difference test (Satorra and Bentler, 2001), we found that the inclusion of the RI factors significantly increased model fit (Model 2 compared to Model 1). Model fit also increased when the RS factors for both the FI and DS entered the model separately, although the improvement in model fit was greater for the FI than for DS (Models 3a and 3b compared to Model 2, respectively). The results, however, indicate that Model 3c (i.e., RI and RS factors for both the FI and DS) provides the best and most parsimonious representation of the data. Even though the model fit statistics favored Model 3c, we report the parameter estimates for Models 1 and 2, too, which facilitates the interpretation of effects and promotes a better understanding to which extent the different model specifications may change conclusions.

3.2.1. Parameter estimates

Parameter estimates with 99.9% confidence intervals (CIs) of Models 1, 2, and 3c can be found in Table 3 (see also Table A2 in the electronic supplementary materials for complete case analysis). In all three models, there are autoregressive effects within both the FI and DS, although Model 1 demonstrates the strongest effects and Model 3c the weakest effects.

As regards the cross-lagged effects, Model 1 shows positive effects of weak to moderate size from the FI to DS. This means that higher FI levels at a specific point in time are related to more DS at a subsequent point in time. If these effects are considered relative to the person-specific mean

Table 1
Descriptive statistics and pairwise correlations across waves.

Variable	N	M (SD)	FI _{w1}	FI _{w2}	FI _{w4}	FI _{w5}	FI _{w6}	FI _{w7}	DS _{w1}	DS _{w2}	DS _{w4}	DS _{w5}	DS _{w6}	DS _{w7}
FI _{w1}	21,677	0.11 (0.11)	(0.89)	19,528	11,929	12,205	11,269	9,910	21,527	19,368	11,636	11,836	10,753	7,722
FI _{w2}	27,370	0.12 (0.12)	0.76	(0.91)	16,890	15,630	15,633	13,796	19,414	27,108	16,547	15,193	14,987	11,162
FI _{w4}	37,390	0.14 (0.13)	0.67	0.72	(0.91)	30,472	27,103	22,749	11,837	16,735	36,803	30,045	26,214	9,621
FI _{w5}	43,466	0.14 (0.14)	0.64	0.68	0.77	(0.93)	35,094	29,563	12,110	15,459	30,074	42,801	34,116	8,897
FI _{w6}	41,626	0.15 (0.14)	0.59	0.65	0.71	0.77	(0.93)	32,569	11,175	15,463	26,730	34,656	40,447	11,431
FI _{w7}	34,375	0.16 (0.15)	0.57	0.61	0.66	0.72	0.79	(0.93)	9,824	13,653	22,467	29,232	31,930	12,024
DS _{w1}	21,536	2.26 (2.18)	0.45	0.38	0.33	0.32	0.29	0.28	(0.74)	19,269	11,554	11,747	10,669	7,651
DS _{w2}	27,141	2.27 (2.24)	0.41	0.51	0.36	0.36	0.33	0.31	0.55	(0.74)	16,404	15,029	14,835	11,073
DS _{w4}	36,824	2.52 (2.24)	0.35	0.39	0.48	0.40	0.37	0.32	0.46	0.50	(0.72)	29,690	25,879	9,522
DS _{w5}	42,854	2.41 (2.23)	0.38	0.40	0.42	0.50	0.41	0.37	0.43	0.46	0.53	(0.73)	33,792	8,813
DS _{w6}	40,461	2.46 (2.25)	0.34	0.37	0.40	0.42	0.50	0.41	0.36	0.41	0.48	0.54	(0.73)	11,240
DS _{w7}	12,031	2.46 (2.31)	0.35	0.37	0.40	0.42	0.44	0.51	0.34	0.39	0.46	0.52	0.57	(0.73)

Notes. In the lower triangle of the correlation matrix, we report pairwise correlations across waves 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, and 7 (w1, w2, w4, w5, w6, and w7) for the frailty index (FI) and the depressive symptoms (DS) score of the EURO-D. The upper triangle of the matrix shows the total number of observations for each variable combination. Reliability estimates (coefficient ω based on tetrachoric correlations) are reported in parenthesis in the diagonal. $M =$ Mean. $SD =$ Standard deviation. $N =$ total number of valid observations for each variable. The considerably lower number of valid observations for DS in wave 7 is due to changes in the SHARE questionnaire structure in 2017, where a substantial group of participants only received a limited set of questions from the regular questionnaire (including the FI items, but excluding the DS items).

Table 2
Model fit statistics of Models 1, 2, 3a, 3b, and 3c.

Model	$\chi^2(df)$	p-value	ref.	$\Delta\chi^2(\Delta df)$	Δp -value	TLI	CFI	SRMR	RMSEA [90% CI]	AIC	BIC
1	11870(50)	<.00001	–	–	–	0.893	0.919	0.110	0.077 [0.076, 0.078]	360888	361120
2	7974(47)	<.00001	1	2594(3)	<.00001	0.927	0.948	0.065	0.064 [0.063, 0.065]	354752	355001
3a	1501(43)	<.00001	2	5570(4)	<.00001	0.986	0.991	0.041	0.028 [0.027, 0.030]	345669	345941
3b	7732(43)	<.00001	2	186(4)	<.00001	0.922	0.949	0.066	0.066 [0.065, 0.067]	354526	354799
3c	469(38)	<.00001	2	7505(9)	<.00001	0.995	0.997	0.013	0.017 [0.015, 0.018]	344267	344568

Note. Model 1 resembles cross-lagged panel modeling without random effects. In Model 2, we included a random intercept factor for both the frailty index (FI) and depressive symptoms (DS). In Models 3a and 3b, we separately included random slope factors for the FI and DS, respectively. In Model 3c, we included random slope factors for both constructs. χ^2 is the model fit test statistic. $\Delta\chi^2(\Delta df)$ is based on the scaled χ^2 -difference test. df = degrees of freedom. ref. = reference model to compare with. TLI = Tucker-Lewis-index. CFI = comparative-fit-index. SRMR = standardized root mean square residual. RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation. AIC = Akaike information criterion. BIC = sample-size adjusted Bayesian information criterion. CI = confidence interval.

levels as specified in Model 2, the cross-lagged structure still shows considerable effects. In other words, individuals who score above their own mean FI levels at a given point in time also tend to score above their own mean DS levels at a subsequent point in time. However, if the individual trends are removed as well (as in Model 3c), the cross-lagged effects decrease considerably in size. As regards the cross-lagged effects from DS to the FI, we found very weak effects in all three models. Therefore, the (within-person) relationship between the FI at a specific point in time and DS at a subsequent point in time seems to be negligible.

Moreover, we found positive within-time associations in all three models. That is, the time-specific measures (i.e., residuals) of the FI and DS show a moderately strong relationship to each other, irrespective of whether the effects are considered relative to the person-specific levels/trends (Models 2 and 3c) or not (Model 1). In other words, individuals who score above the person-(or group)-specific FI levels (and trends) also tend to score above the person-(or group)-specific DS levels (and trends) at the same point in time.

Next to the within-person effects, Model 3c provides further information on the between-person effects of the random factors. First of all, the model-implied initial levels of the FI and DS are 0.11 and 2.23, respectively. Second, within two consecutive waves, the increase in the FI is 0.01 (CI [0.01, 0.01]), and the DS score increases on average by 0.07 (CI [0.07, 0.08]). Third, the RI and RS factors of the FI and DS show a relatively strong, positive relationship with each other: individuals with higher initial levels in the FI tend to show higher initial levels in DS, and individuals with steeper trajectories in the FI tend to show steeper trajectories in DS as well. Finally, there is a moderately strong, negative relationship between the RI and RS factors of DS, which means that higher initial levels go along with less steep trajectories in DS.

3.2.2. Multiple group analysis

Multiple group analysis was performed based on the specification in Model 3c. Models including sex did not reveal considerable differences in within-person effects (see Table A3 in the electronic supplementary materials). The means of the RI factors, however, differed across sex: Females demonstrated higher initial levels in both the FI and DS. The means of the RS factors differed for DS (but not for the FI): DS trajectories tend to be somewhat steeper in females than in males. The correlations between the RI and RS factors are of similar size in men and women.

As regards multiple group analysis in terms of age, the results showed no notable differences in within-person effects (see Table A4 in the electronic supplementary materials). Not surprisingly, the means of the RI factors for the FI increase with increasing age. The RI for DS shows a higher mean value in the 50–55 age group and in individuals older than 65 years, compared to the other two age groups. The correlations between the random FI and DS intercepts, as well as between the random FI and DS slopes were somewhat higher in individuals older than 65 years than in individuals aged between 50 and 55 years.

Multiple group analysis concerning the different educational levels also showed no considerable differences in within-person effects (see Table A5 in the electronic supplementary materials). But, there are

considerable differences in the between-person effects of the random factors. The initial levels of both the FI and DS decreased with increasing educational level. Moreover, the trajectories of both the FI and DS were steeper in lower educated individuals, compared to medium and high educated individuals. It also showed that the correlation between the random FI and DS slopes is greater in higher educated individuals than in lower educated individuals.

4. Discussion

Frailty and depression both cause suffering and can represent a major burden for individuals, families, and institutions. To develop strategies specifically targeted to lower this burden and to maintain well-being in late life, a detailed examination of the causes, effects, and interdependencies of these physical and mental health states is warranted. This study contributes to the literature in that it examined to which extent the relationship between frailty and depression can be explained by (1) reciprocal influences of these variables, (2) common causes, or (3) both (1) and (2). The modeling approach used in this study allowed us to disentangle the processes that happen within individuals from differences that manifest between individuals. Doing so is crucial, as this approach permits us to evaluate whether changes in one health domain indeed initiate changes in another health domain within the same individual.

In this respect, we tested five hypotheses that are interpreted in terms of the different levels of analysis. As regards the hypothesis of whether frailty deteriorations at a specific point in time increases the risk of future depression (H1a), the findings vary due to differences in model specification. While Models 1 and 2 demonstrated a weak to moderate statistical effect of frailty on depression, the effect in Model 3c was too low to provide convincing support for this hypothesis. Since the cross-lagged component in these models captures regression effects of the deviations from what is considered *normal*, the diverging findings across models result from different conceptualizations of normality. While Model 1 takes the average value of the entire sample as a reference point, Models 2 and 3c make each individual to his or her own reference point. More specifically, in Model 2 it is assumed that the individual frailty and depression levels remain relatively stable across time and the time-specific fluctuations around these baseline levels are modeled. In Model 3c, however, the individual frailty and depression levels are allowed to have a linear trend across time and the model takes the person-specific long-term trajectories as a reference point.

From a theoretical point of view, the specification in Model 3c seems to be the most appropriate one. The assumptions that individuals do not considerably differ in their initial frailty and depression levels and that these levels do not change across time does not seem to hold well, particularly in late life (e.g., Hoogendijk et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2019; Sutin et al., 2013). Therefore, Model 3c seems to provide a more adequate representation of the fundamental aging process, wherein individual differences in both the levels and trajectories of frailty and depression are specifically taken into account. In this case, the time-specific fluctuations around the individual long-term trajectories

Table 3
Parameter estimates of Models 1, 2, and 3c.

Parameter	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3c
Random effects: Means			
Intercept FI*	0.13 [0.13, 0.14]	0.13 [0.13, 0.13]	0.11 [0.10, 0.11]
Intercept DS*	2.40 [2.37, 2.43]	2.39 [2.36, 2.42]	2.23 [2.20, 2.27]
Slope FI	–	–	0.69 [0.62, 0.76]
Slope DS	–	–	0.28 [0.24, 0.33]
Random effects: Correlations			
ζ_1 (intercept FI ↔ intercept DS)	–	0.65 [0.63, 0.67]	0.56 [0.50, 0.62]
ζ_2 (intercept FI ↔ slope FI)	–	–	0.14 [–0.01, 0.30]
ζ_3 (intercept FI ↔ slope DS)	–	–	0.07 [–0.06, 0.20]
ζ_4 (intercept DS ↔ slope FI)	–	–	0.09 [–0.02, 0.20]
ζ_5 (intercept DS ↔ slope DS)	–	–	–0.32 [–0.43, –0.21]
ζ_6 (slope FI ↔ slope DS)	–	–	0.50 [0.38, 0.62]
Autoregressive (FI → FI)			
α_1	0.73 [0.71, 0.75]	0.21 [0.13, 0.30]	0.13 [–0.07, 0.33]
α_2	0.69 [0.67, 0.72]	0.28 [0.22, 0.34]	0.19 [0.12, 0.26]
α_3	0.75 [0.74, 0.76]	0.55 [0.52, 0.58]	0.26 [0.21, 0.30]
α_5	0.78 [0.77, 0.79]	0.64 [0.61, 0.67]	0.20 [0.14, 0.26]
α_5	0.80 [0.79, 0.82]	0.69 [0.67, 0.72]	0.15 [0.04, 0.26]
Autoregressive (DS → DS)			
β_1	0.46 [0.44, 0.48]	0.21 [0.17, 0.25]	0.04 [–0.06, 0.14]
β_2	0.43 [0.40, 0.46]	0.11 [0.07, 0.15]	0.06 [0.01, 0.11]
β_3	0.46 [0.44, 0.48]	0.17 [0.13, 0.20]	0.13 [0.09, 0.16]
β_4	0.46 [0.45, 0.48]	0.19 [0.16, 0.22]	0.11 [0.07, 0.15]
β_5	0.47 [0.44, 0.50]	0.24 [0.20, 0.28]	0.08 [–0.00, 0.15]
Cross-lagged (FI → DS)			
δ_1	0.20 [0.18, 0.23]	0.07 [0.02, 0.12]	0.06 [–0.07, 0.18]
δ_2	0.18 [0.15, 0.20]	0.08 [0.02, 0.13]	0.06 [0.00, 0.11]
δ_3	0.22 [0.20, 0.24]	0.21 [0.17, 0.24]	0.05 [0.02, 0.09]
δ_4	0.23 [0.21, 0.25]	0.27 [0.23, 0.30]	0.07 [0.02, 0.12]
δ_5	0.25 [0.21, 0.28]	0.26 [0.21, 0.31]	0.04 [–0.05, 0.13]
Cross-lagged (DS → FI)			
γ_1	0.05 [0.03, 0.07]	0.04 [–0.01, 0.08]	0.06 [–0.02, 0.14]
γ_2	0.04 [0.02, 0.06]	0.04 [0.00, 0.08]	0.03 [–0.01, 0.08]
γ_3	0.06 [0.05, 0.08]	0.07 [0.04, 0.09]	0.05 [0.02, 0.08]
γ_4	0.05 [0.03, 0.06]	0.04 [0.02, 0.06]	0.03 [–0.00, 0.07]
γ_5	0.03 [0.02, 0.05]	0.04 [0.01, 0.06]	0.03 [–0.04, 0.09]
Within-time (FI ↔ DS)			
λ_1	0.45 [0.43, 0.47]	0.21 [0.16, 0.26]	0.24 [0.09, 0.38]
λ_2	0.32 [0.29, 0.35]	0.33 [0.30, 0.37]	0.34 [0.28, 0.39]
λ_3	0.34 [0.32, 0.37]	0.34 [0.31, 0.37]	0.28 [0.25, 0.31]
λ_4	0.32 [0.30, 0.34]	0.36 [0.33, 0.38]	0.28 [0.25, 0.31]
λ_5	0.30 [0.28, 0.32]	0.32 [0.30, 0.35]	0.26 [0.21, 0.31]
λ_6	0.32 [0.28, 0.35]	0.34 [0.30, 0.37]	0.29 [0.21, 0.36]

Note. We report the standardized parameter estimates and the 99.9% confidence intervals (CIs, in parenthesis) for all variables except for the means of the random intercepts, for which the unstandardized estimates are reported. FI = frailty index. DS = depressive symptoms. *unstandardized effects.

do not provide any further considerable information to corroborate the notion that frailty results in future depression at the within-person level. The relative superiority of Model 3c was further supported by the fact that this model showed the best statistical fit and the greatest parsimony.

For hypothesis *H1b*, that is, whether the worsening of depression can be considered as a risk factor for future deteriorations in frailty, the findings are more consistent across models. Although the point estimates of each model are in the expected direction, the effects are generally very weak and the practical relevance is negligible. Therefore, these results do not support the assumption that there is a direct link between depression and future frailty deteriorations.

Hypothesis *H2* states that worsening depression goes along with simultaneous increases in frailty. This hypothesis was strongly supported by the data, with moderate effects of similar size across models. In terms of Model 3c, this means that an individual that shows a deviation in frailty above his or her long-term trajectory tends to show a deviation in depression above his or her long-term trajectory at the same point in time. Since these effects represent time-specific correlations at the within-person level, this finding might indicate confounding due to time-varying third variables or, in other words, the existence of occasional common causes or influences. One possible explanation for this phenomenon might be that specific circumstances (e.g., new medication) account for simultaneous changes in both mental and physical states (or the perception thereof), which, as a result, shows in a positive correlation at a specific point in time.

As regards hypothesis *H3* and *H4*, we found robust and relatively strong intercept-intercept and slope-slope associations: individuals who show higher initial levels of frailty are at greater risk to also demonstrate higher initial levels of depression, and individuals with stronger declines in frailty tend to demonstrate more severe deteriorations in depression over time. The arising question is what individuals which show higher levels and/or steeper trajectories in both frailty and depression have in common, or in other words, what are the common causes that have a similar impact on both variables. In contrast to the time-specific correlations at the within-person level (which are likely due to time-varying influences as reported above), the underlying causes concerning the between-person correlations refer to rather stable factors and might comprise biological, psychosocial, behavioral, and environmental factors. For example, dysfunction in basic systems of the body (e.g., autonomic nervous system dysfunction as indexed by low heart rate variability) might trigger a cascade of processes not only resulting in more physiological deficits (Varadhan et al., 2009) but also in more depressive symptoms (Hartmann et al., 2019). In a similar vein, psychosocial factors such as specific personality traits (e.g., neuroticism) or loneliness might indicate vulnerability factors for both higher levels and more severe progressions in both constructs (Gale et al., 2018; Hakulinen et al., 2015; Holvast et al., 2015; Stephan et al., 2017; Steunenberget al., 2006). Due to a lack of relevant data, the current study only provides limited information on potential underlying factors. Since we found the between-person correlations to vary as a function of age (see also Ji et al., 2020) and educational level, it is likely that factors related to these covariates might play a role in this context. The underlying mechanisms in the frailty-depression link will have to be further explored by future research.

To summarize, our study findings question the notion that frailty and depression each initiate future changes in the other construct, but rather indicate that these physical and mental health states might be two sides of the same coin. This pattern is in line with the reasoning of previous research arguing for a shared vulnerability of frailty and depression (Lohman et al., 2014, 2016; Mezuk et al., 2013), but contradicts a bulk of research that indeed demonstrated uni- or bi-directional effects (for

reviews, see Mezuk et al., 2012; Soysal et al., 2017; Vaughan et al., 2015). Nonetheless, comparability of the current study to previous research is restricted, since the majority of studies in this context only relies on cross-sectional or two-wave longitudinal data (Soysal et al., 2017), or did not explicitly separate the within-person changes from the between-person variability (e.g., Bacon et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2012; Luo et al., 2019).

4.1. Limitations and strengths of this study

Nevertheless, since this study is based on secondary data analysis, some other limitations exist as well. Potential reasons for the fact that we did not find considerable, reciprocal effects of frailty and depression might be the few observations per individual, the long intervals between measurements, and sample attrition that is due to unobserved causes (e.g., hospitalization or death). Future studies might also consider mixture modeling to reveal latent groups of Individuals who show differential effects in the within-person cross-lagged structure. Strengths of this study are the advanced modeling approach, the large representative database, and the long period under investigation.

5. Conclusions

This study did *not* demonstrate evidence for a reciprocal relationship between frailty and depression at the within-person level. Still, long-term increases in frailty were shown to be related to long-term increases in depression at the between-person level, which likely indicates the existence of a shared vulnerability. The disaggregation of within- and between-person effects emerged as a valuable approach to study the relationship between frailty and depression, and brings us closer to resolving the question whether there is a causal link between these physical and mental health states in older age. The evidence for such a causal relationship was scarce in our study, but rather indicated that frailty and depression might be both determined by common causes, in both the short and the long term.

CRedit author statement

Hannes Mayerl: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. Erwin Stolz: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing. Wolfgang Freidl: Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

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Data accessibility statement

Access to the data collected and generated in the SHARE projects is provided free of charge for scientific use globally. The SHARE data can be downloaded after successful registration from “<http://www.share-project.org>”.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there are no actual or potential conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113273>.

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